

DELISA **LTO**

DESCRIPTION OF THE EXTENDED LIFETIME AND ITS INFLUENCE ON THE SAFETY OPERATION AND CONSTRUCTION MATERIALS PERFORMANCE – LONG TERM OPERATION WITH NO COMPROMISES IN THE

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SEM measurements

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List of abbreviations

BSE	Backscattered Electron
EDS	Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy
MCP	Main Circulation Pipe
NPP	Nuclear Power Plant
SE	Secondary electron
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscopy
SG	Steam Generator

1. Introduction to SEM

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) is a surface imaging and microstructural analysis technique based on the interaction of a focused electron beam with the sample surface. It provides high-resolution images of the microstructure and allows observation of grain morphology, boundaries, cracks, pores, precipitates, and secondary phases. With backscattered electron (BSE) detection, compositional contrast is obtained, while secondary electron (SE) imaging highlights topographical features.

In addition to imaging, SEM is often equipped with an Energy-Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy (EDS) module, which enables semi-quantitative chemical composition analysis of the examined areas. When the electron beam interacts with the sample, characteristic X-rays are emitted from the atoms in the interaction volume. These X-rays are detected by the EDS system and converted into an energy spectrum, where each peak corresponds to a specific element. EDS thus allows identification of elements present in the material and approximate determination of their local concentrations.

The combined use of SEM imaging and EDS analysis is crucial for studying long-term operated nuclear steels, as it provides simultaneous information on microstructural morphology (e.g., grain boundaries, inclusions, precipitates, cracks) and local chemical inhomogeneities (e.g., Cr-rich or Ni-depleted regions, segregation zones, or secondary phase formation).

During long-term thermal exposure at ~ 300 °C, low-alloy steels and austenitic stainless steels are expected to undergo characteristic ageing changes. In low-alloy steels, segregation of alloying elements (Cr, Mo, Ni) to grain boundaries and the precipitation of carbides such as $M_{23}C_6$ or M_6C may occur, followed by coarsening and recovery of bainitic/martensitic substructures, which leads to softening and toughness loss [1]. In austenitic stainless steels (e.g., 08Ch18N10T, 08Ch18N12T), chromium carbide precipitation at grain boundaries and chromium/nickel depletion in adjacent regions promote sensitisation and intergranular corrosion [2]. Prolonged exposure may also cause Ni segregation and partial $\gamma \rightarrow \alpha$ transformation, contributing to embrittlement and microcrack initiation [3]. SEM/EDS analysis thus provides direct evidence of these processes by revealing precipitates, segregation zones, and intergranular damage that complement mechanical test results.

1.1 Measuring device – Hitachi SU3500

SEM investigations were performed using a Hitachi SU3500 scanning electron microscope, which enables both high-resolution imaging and complementary analytical techniques. The instrument is equipped with secondary electron and backscattered electron detectors, allowing detailed characterisation of surface topography and compositional contrast. In addition, the system supports EDS for semi-quantitative chemical analysis.

The technical performance of the SU3500 ensures reliable analysis across a wide range of operating conditions. The resolution reaches 3 nm at 30 kV accelerating voltage (WD = 5 mm, high-vacuum mode) and 7 nm at 3 kV (WD = 5 mm, high-vacuum mode) in SE mode. The available magnification range extends from $\times 5$ up to $\times 300\,000$, enabling both overview imaging and nanoscale observations.

1.2 Test protocol

All samples were prepared by grinding, polishing, and final surface finishing prior to SEM investigation. Most specimens were electropolished and etched with K1 electrolyte (QATM company) to reveal grain boundaries, while for selected materials (e.g., no.6c, no.7, no.8, no.8-SS) plasma polishing in a NaCl bath was used due to complications with conventional electropolishing.

SEM analysis was performed using a Hitachi SU3500 equipped with SE detectors. SE imaging was primarily employed for surface morphology and etching response. Imaging was typically performed at accelerating voltages of 3–5 kV (SE mode) with working distances of 5–15 mm, at magnifications ranging from $\times 300$ to $\times 1500$ for microstructural overview, and up to $\times 20\,000$ for detailed inspection. EDS was applied to multiple points, line scans, and selected areas of each sample to characterise local chemical composition and elemental segregation.

2. Materials and Specimens

SEM and EDS measurement were used for the measurement of the DELISA-LTO samples specified in Deliverable D2.2 - Database of the available material. The partial description is in Tab.1.

Table 1. Investigated materials.

No	Sample	Reactor Type	Steel Grade	Operational Status
1	Main circulation piping	VVER -440	08Ch18N12T	initial state (V1 NPP)
2	Pressurizer surge line	VVER -440	08Ch18N10T	initial state (EBO3 NPP)
3a	Main circulation piping	VVER -440	08Ch18N12T	operated at 294 °C for 28 years (V1 NPP)
5	Pressurizer surge line	VVER -1000	08Ch18N10T	operated at 274 °C for 28 years (V1 NPP)
6c	Reactor flange fastening parts - stud	VVER -1000	38KhN3MFA	operated at 305 °C for 30 years (IPP-C)
7	Steam generator collector with HE tubes	VVER -1000	08Ch18N10T/ 10GN2MFA	operated at 280-315 °C (IPP-C)
8	Main circulation piping	VVER -1000	10GN2MFA +SS cladding	initial state (IPP-C)
9a	Capsules of the thermal specimens	VVER -440	08Ch18N10T	operated at 278 °C for 24 years (Paks NPP)

9b				operated at 278 °C for 32 years (Paks NPP)
10	Main circulation pump - Guide wheel	VVER -440	10H18N9TL	operated for 27 years (EK-CER)

Specimens represent primary circuit components and long-term aged surveillance/auxiliary materials spanning austenitic stainless steels (08Ch18N10T/12T, 10H18N9TL), low-alloy ferritic steels (10GN2MFA), and welded/cladded joints characteristic of WWER-440/1000 plants. The set captures:

- base metal 08Ch18N12T before operation (sample no.1) and after 28 years of operation in NPP (sample no.3)
- base metal 08Ch18N10T before operation (sample no.2) and after 28 years of operation in NPP (sample no.5) vs. welded metal (sample no.7) vs. sample with stainless cladding (sample no.8),
- long-term thermal ageing effects and phase redistribution in 08Ch18N10T (samples no.9a and no.9b),
- rotating component service exposure in chlorinated/borated primary water (Sample no.10),
- fastening components under sustained preload and thermal transients (no.6).

The investigated samples were in the shape of SPT samples with a diameter of 8 mm or small prisms with parameters of 8 mm x 8 mm x 0.5 mm. Samples' surface was ground into a mirror level. For microscopy investigations, the samples were prepared by electro-polishing or, where necessary, by plasma polishing to ensure a high-quality surface finish.

3. Results

SEM results are presented as figures with scale between 500 and 30 μm and EDS line scans performed across selected microstructure. The same materials were compared with respect to their response to thermal ageing and operation history. The detailed EDS analysis for the sample at local points is attached in the ANNEX.

Results for sample no.1 and no.3a (08Ch18N12T) are showed and compared in Fig. 1, Fig.2 and Fig.3. Sample no.1 shows equiaxed austenitic grains with sizes of about 50–200 μm and relatively homogeneous chemical composition, consistent with a solution-annealed state. The grain boundaries were clearly visible, with only minor carbon residues attributed to the electropolishing process. By contrast, sample no.3a (after 28 years at ~294 °C) revealed somewhat refined grains of 100–200 μm with clearer boundaries. EDS analysis indicated small variations in Cr and Ni, with slight nickel depletion at boundaries. These features are consistent with the onset of thermal ageing and sensitisation effects, although the bulk microstructure remained predominantly austenitic.

Fig.1. SEM results for sample no.1 (a) and sample no.3a (b).

Fig.2. EDS results for sample no.1.

Fig.3. EDS results for sample no.3a.

Sample No.2 displayed grains of 20–100 μm and a homogeneous Cr–Ni distribution. The carbon-rich surface networks were identified as residues from electropolishing. In contrast, sample No.5 showed significantly smaller grains (10–70 μm) and greater heterogeneity in chemical composition. Local analyses indicated higher Cr values in some regions (up to ~24 wt.%), accompanied by lower Ni concentrations, which indicates local segregation and possible ferrite formation. These microstructural changes suggest more pronounced ageing-related effects in the pressurizer surge line material compared to the main circulation piping.

Fig.4. SEM results for sample no.2 (a) and sample no.5 (b).

Fig.5. EDS results for sample no.2.

Fig.6. EDS results for sample no.5.

Microstructure of sample No.6 (Fig. 7a and 8, WWER-1000, reactor fastening parts - nuts) remained predominantly austenitic with grains $\sim 20\text{--}50\ \mu\text{m}$. Local Cr enrichment and Ni depletion at boundaries indicate the onset of sensitisation.

In sample no.7 (Fig. 7b and 9, SG collector after operation in WWER-1000) were observed very fine grains ($\sim 3\text{--}10\ \mu\text{m}$). Despite minor segregation trends, the structure is largely stable and austenitic.

The results for no.6 and no.7 show ageing influence at boundaries but no significant phase transformation.

Fig.7. SEM results for sample no.6 (a) and sample no.7 (b).

Fig.8. EDS results for sample no.6.

Fig.8. EDS results for sample no.7.

The austenitic part of the sample No.8 (Fig.10a and Fig.11, WWER-1000 -MCP piping) was investigated. Grains of 10–30 μm with austenitic morphology was found there. EDS revealed Cr variations and slight Ni depletion at some points, but no secondary phases were confirmed. Ageing effects are visible mainly as boundary segregation, while the bulk remains austenitic.

In sample No.10 (Fig.10b and Fig.12, WWER-440, main circulation pump guide wheel, 27 years of service), coarse grains of 50–100 μm were observed. EDS showed heterogeneous Cr (16–27 wt.%) and Ni (4–10 wt.%) contents, indicating stronger segregation than in other samples. Despite these variations, the microstructure is still dominated by austenite, with ageing manifested by boundary sensitisation rather than transformation.

Fig.10. SEM results for sample no.8 (a) and sample no.10 (b).

Fig.11. EDS results for sample no.8(SS).

Fig.12. EDS results for sample no.10.

Comparison of samples No.9a and No.9b (Fig.13 - Fig.15, WWER-440, thermal capsules, 24 vs. 32 years of service) exhibited similar austenitic matrix in both with visible grain boundaries and grain sizes of 10–50 μm . In sample No.9a, EDS analyses confirmed Fe–Cr–Ni composition close to nominal values, with only minor local variations. Grain boundaries were distinct but compact, showing limited segregation effects. In contrast, sample No.9b displayed more pronounced compositional heterogeneity: chromium enrichment and nickel depletion were systematically observed at grain boundaries, suggesting more advanced segregation. The bulk

microstructure remained austenitic, but the degree of boundary sensitisation and local heterogeneity increased with longer exposure.

In samples no.9, local material loss was observed at grain boundaries. This feature may be attributed either to mechanical preparation artefacts during electropolishing or to real degradation phenomena such as intergranular corrosion associated with chromium depletion and nickel segregation.”

Overall, the comparison demonstrates that prolonged thermal ageing (32 vs. 24 years) enhances boundary segregation and chemical redistribution without yet leading to a complete phase transformation, but it indicates progression toward microstructural degradation processes relevant to long-term service.

Fig.13. SEM results for sample no.9a (a) and sample no.9b (b).

Fig.14. EDS results for sample no.9a.

Fig.15. EDS results for sample no.9b.

4. Summary

SEM investigations showed that the overall microstructure of both austenitic stainless steels and low-alloy steels remains relatively stable after long-term service, with grains and phases largely preserved. The main ageing effects were observed at grain boundaries, where local segregation and compositional heterogeneity were detected. In austenitic steels, SEM/EDS indicated chromium enrichment and nickel depletion at boundaries, which are known precursors for the local transformation of austenite into ferrite during extended thermal exposure. No large-scale phase changes were observed within the studied timescales; however, boundary sensitisation, segregation trends, and surface heterogeneity confirm the early stages of degradation. SEM thus provides valuable complementary evidence of thermal ageing by visualising microstructural stability, detecting local phase redistribution, and linking these features to long-term material performance.

5. Bibliography

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6. ANNEX

Sample no. 1

Spectrum Label	Nr. 1	Nr. 2	Nr.3	Nr. 4	Nr. 5	Nr. 6	Nr. 7	Nr. 8	Nr. 9	Nr. 10	Nr. 11	Nr. 12
C	2.11	2.9	3.64	3.32	2.9	3.13	3.15	2.96	3.2	2.75	3.13	3.42
Al		0.15		0.23	0.2						0.16	
Si	0.11	0.42	0.52	0.48	0.47	0.48	0.54	0.51	0.48	0.5	0.5	0.47
Ti	0.62	0.41	0.24	0.38	0.53	0.37	0.52	0.39	0.43	0.44	0.54	0.54
Cr	21.5	19	17.7	17.4	17.8	17.9	17.6	17.7	17.7	17.96	17.71	17.4
Mn	1.79	1.16	1.31	1.21	1.25	1.07	1.08	1.17	1.21	1.21	1.26	1.2
Fe	66.9	65.7	64.9	64.9	65.2	65.5	65.3	65.4	65.1	65.27	65.25	65.34
Ni	6.92	10.3	11.8	12	11.6	11.5	11.9	11.9	11.9	11.87	11.46	11.61

Sample no. 2

Spectrum Label	Nr. 13	Nr. 14	Nr. 15	Nr. 16	Nr. 17	Nr. 18	Nr. 19	Nr. 20	Nr. 21	Nr. 22	Nr. 23	Nr. 24	Nr. 25
C	2.34	3.6	2.87	2.81	2.88	2.95	2.96	2.89	2.73	2.78	2.85	2.54	2.8
Al		0.16	0.15					0.2		0.25			0.17
Si	0.26	0.39	0.46	0.49	0.42	0.46	0.49	0.48	0.49	0.42	0.45	0.36	0.48
Ti	5.4	0.42	0.46	0.41	0.45	0.25	0.39	0.34	0.47	0.42	0.46	0.33	0.39
Cr	17.8	17.32	16.96	17.2	17.4	17.15	17.7	17.18	17.02	16.89	17	17.9	17.1
Mn	1.78	1.74	1.74	1.79	1.7	1.82	1.49	1.66	1.76	1.8	1.67	1.82	1.7
Fe	63.79	66.99	67.2	67.44	67.35	67.76	67.52	67.5	66.66	67.35	67.32	67.98	67.2
Ni	8.63	9.38	10.17	9.85	9.79	9.61	9.44	9.77	10.87	10.1	10.25	9.07	10.17

Sample no.3a

Spectrum Label	Nr. 26	Nr. 27	Nr. 28	Nr. 29	Nr. 30	Nr. 31	Nr. 32	Nr. 33	Nr. 34	Nr. 35	Nr. 36	Nr. 37	Nr. 38
C	3.3	2.73	3.16	2.63	3.31	3	3.12	3.16	2.92	3.71	2.96	3.54	3.25
O		0.79											
Si	0.43	0.32	0.39	0.39	0.47	0.41	0.45	0.38	0.43	0.46	0.4	0.44	0.47
Ti	0.44	0.4	0.34	0.29	0.32	0.29	0.3		0.39	0.33	0.35	0.21	0.28
Cr	17.92	18.56	17.54	18.19	18.11	17.99	18.04	17.84	18.01	18.1	18.2	17.98	17.83
Mn	1.38	1.39	1.51	1.54	1.46	1.21	1.34	1.58	1.56	1.3	1.6	1.39	1.64
Fe	64.89	64.8	65.07	65.32	65.13	64.56	65.55	65.68	65.24	64.34	64.82	64.75	64.95
Ni	11.63	11.03	11.99	11.66	11.2	12.54	11.2	11.36	11.45	11.76	11.66	11.69	11.58

Sample no.5

Spectrum	Nr. 39	Nr. 40	Nr. 41	Nr. 42	Nr. 43	Nr. 44	Nr. 45	Nr. 46	Nr. 47	Nr. 48	Nr. 49	Nr. 50	Nr. 51	Nr. 52	Nr. 53
C	4.01	4.29	3.06	3.15	4.72	6.15	3.17	3.01	3.07	4.87	2.76	3	3.18	3.02	4.6
O					0.92	1.02				2					1.13
Si	0.44	0.45	0.39	0.4	0.4	0.52	0.38	0.44	0.46	0.41	0.41	0.4	0.38	0.39	0.36
Ti	0.69	0.39	0.43	0.35	0.49	0.33	0.4	0.43	0.36	1.08	0.38	0.33	0.46	0.46	0.74
Cr	18.48	17.31	18.31	18.39	17.81	24.65	17.57	17.51	17.64	16.98	18.03	17.57	17.62	18.25	17.72
Mn	1.31	1.46	1.45	1.53	1.64	1.06	1.54	1.38	1.38	1.37	1.49	1.43	1.39	1.25	1.35
Fe	66.59	66.39	67.2	67.15	65.6	61.98	66.87	67	66.82	63.44	66.77	67.41	67.05	67.14	64.88
Ni	8.49	9.71	9.16	9.02	8.41	4.3	10.09	10.24	10.27	9.51	10.16	9.86	9.9	9.48	9.22

Sample no.6c

Spectrum Label	Nr. 1	Nr. 2	Nr. 3	Nr. 4	Nr. 5	Nr. 6	Nr. 7	Nr. 8	Nr. 9
C	10.15	4.38	7.36	6.55	7.64	17.48	5.53	10.43	3.66
O	1.88			1.7	3.09	4.96		2.75	
Si	0.21	0.3	0.33	0.3	0.26	0.24	0.26	0.28	0.25
S	0.32		0.25	0.35	0.78	0.75		0.57	
V				0.28	0.45	0.56	0.24	0.28	
Cr	1.88	1.47	1.88	2	3.35	4.19	1.74	2.37	1.43
Mn	0.5		0.53	0.52	0.69	0.91	0.58	0.66	0.4
Fe	81.57	90.52	86.26	85.16	79.11	64.21	87.07	79.52	90.7
Ni	3.49	2.8	3.39	3.15	3.82	4.12	3.6	3.15	2.96
Cu					0.81	1.25			
Mo		0.53				1.34	0.97		

Sample no.7

Spectrum Label	Nr. 10	Nr. 11	Nr. 12	Nr. 13	Nr. 14	Nr. 15	Nr. 16	Nr. 17	Nr. 18	Nr. 19
C	4.36	3.81	16.57	3.58	11.37	3.88	4.56	5.37	11.89	4.2
O			3.35		2.74				2.76	
Si	0.35	0.35	0.3	0.29	0.29	0.28	0.36	0.33	0.36	0.39
S			0.7		0.6	0.3		0.47	0.67	0.24
Cr	0.39	0.3	0.45	0.33	0.35	0.33	0.35	0.33	0.37	0.25
Mn	1.31	1.36	1.09	1.15	1.31	1.38	1.48	1.35	0.98	1.22
Fe	90.22	91.03	74.18	91.52	79.87	91.37	90.1	89.24	79.41	91.62
Ni	2.56	2.34	3.35	2.65	3.47	2.45	2.46	2.9	3.57	2.08
Mo	0.83	0.81		0.47			0.69			

Sample no.8 – Bulk

Spectrum Label	Nr. 20	Nr. 21	Nr. 22	Nr. 23	Nr. 24	Nr. 25	Nr. 26	Nr. 27	Nr. 28	Nr. 29
C	23.05	19.58	17.96	3.41	3.42	3.63	4.13	3.33	3.77	3.39
O	4.07	3.82	3.09							
Si	0.17	0.23	0.23	0.24	0.23	0.28	0.22	0.25	0.19	0.17
S	0.68	0.58	0.48			0.16		0.19	0.22	
Cr	0.37	0.26	0.32		0.25	0.33		0.23	0.26	0.28
Mn	0.76	0.68	0.67	0.92	0.78	0.78	0.86	0.82	0.89	0.89
Fe	67.73	71.73	74.26	93.19	92.32	92.57	91.88	92.77	92.46	92.6
Ni	3.16	2.78	2.98	1.66	2.02	2.24	2.11	2.41	2.21	1.86
Mo				0.59	0.98		0.79			0.64

Sample no.8 – austenitic cladding

Spectrum Label	Nr. 30	Nr. 31	Nr. 32	Nr. 33	Nr. 34	Nr. 35	Nr. 36	Nr. 37	Nr. 38	Nr. 39	Nr. 40
C	4.72	3.7	4.46	2.97	2.65	2.99	2.96	3.09	3.21	2.92	2.83
O	3.09	0.96	2.96								
Al	0.16	0.21		0.19	0.18	0.16				0.2	
Si	0.26	0.28	0.33	0.32	0.28	0.33	0.34	0.47	0.39	0.33	0.3
Cr	16.14	16.11	16.83	16.43	16.3	17.29	16.47	24.37	18.17	16.44	16.51
Mn	2.14	2.52	2.26	2.39	2.38	2.38	2.42	2.26	2.4	2.38	2.46
Fe	65.81	66.83	64.79	68.73	68.14	69.02	67.64	66.15	67.61	68.13	68.87
Ni	5.89	8.9	6.39	8.48	9.58	7.23	9.59	3.66	7.53	9.13	9.02
Nb	1.16	0.48	1.97	0.48	0.49	0.6	0.58		0.69	0.47	

Sample no.9a

Spectrum Label	Nr. 41	Nr. 42	Nr. 43	Nr. 44	Nr. 45	Nr. 46	Nr. 47	Nr. 48	Nr. 49	Nr. 50
C	7	2.99	3.05	2.84	2.79	3.03	2.54	2.65	2.59	2.61
Al		0.18		0.24	0.17	0.18	0.25	0.18		0.17
Si	0.33	0.45	0.46	0.46	0.47	0.49	0.48	0.53	0.47	0.38
Ti	25.11		0.4	0.25		0.22		0.3	0.21	0.46
Cr	10.68	17.37	17.56	17.18	17.86	17.85	17.87	18.28	17.62	17.53
Mn	0.82	1.39	1.4	1.67	1.4	1.68	1.66	1.33	1.65	1.72
Fe	36.62	68.33	67.54	67.86	68.59	68.18	68.33	68.4	67.99	67.46
Ni	4.97	9.29	9.59	9.51	8.72	8.36	8.86	8.33	8.4	9.04

Sample no.9b

Spectrum Label	Nr. 51	Nr. 52	Nr. 53	Nr. 54	Nr. 55	Nr. 56	Nr. 57	Nr. 58	Nr. 59	Nr. 60	Nr. 61
C	3.03	3.09	2.81	3.19	3.05	3.1	3.13	2.99	3.48	3.27	3.01
Al	0.23	0.15	0.17	0.25	0.24		0.22		0.23	0.2	0.23
Si	0.43	0.38	0.39	0.4	0.38	0.41	0.39	0.34	0.41	0.35	0.45
Ti	0.4	0.41	0.28	0.37	0.3	0.26	2.4	0.32	0.55	0.36	0.28
Cr	18.16	17.67	17.81	17.57	17.43	17.71	17.29	18.07	17.28	17.56	17.69
Mn	1.27	1.25	1.24	1.26	1.22	1.34	1.3	1.38	1.21	1.1	1.31
Fe	66.96	66.51	67.72	66.31	66.88	66.49	65.56	67.09	66.33	67.05	66.8
Ni	9.53	10.54	9.58	10.67	10.5	10.28	9.71	9.81	10.51	10.1	10.24

Sample no.10

Spectrum Label	Nr. 63	Nr. 64	Nr. 65	Nr. 66	Nr. 67	Nr. 68	Nr. 69	Nr. 70	Nr. 71	Nr. 72	Nr. 73
C	2.95	18.01	3.13	2.82	3.01	3.97	8.78	3.35	3.26	3.41	11.57
Al		0.14	0.22	0.19	0.19		0.17	0.17	0.16		
Si	0.57	0.48	0.55	0.54	0.58	0.52	0.54	0.55	0.56	0.53	0.62
Ti	0.24	0.2				0.26					
Cr	18.88	15.95	18.56	18.86	26.89	18.96	17.53	18.88	18.51	18.63	23.87
Mn	1.66	1.27	1.22	1.4	1.3	1.74	1.69	1.6	1.58	1.59	1.2
Fe	66.56	56.08	67.11	66.66	63.67	66.11	62.93	66.36	66.8	66.48	57.51
Ni	9.14	7.46	9.21	9.53	4.36	8.44	8.37	9.11	9.14	9.36	3.96